

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: JAPAN

The Lake Biwa Museum – a window into the geology, history and life of an ancient Japanese lake

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Lake Biwa, located in a monsoon area in east Asia, is the largest lake in Japan, with a surface area of 670 km², and a maximum depth of 104 m. Lake Biwa is divided into two basins – the wide and deep north basin, and the narrower and shallower south basin. The surface area and mean water depth of the north basin are 618 km² and 43 m and those of the south basin are 52 km² and 4 m, respectively. Lake Biwa

of the lake, and provide exhibitions and experience programs that will entice visitors to explore the local area. The LBM is a Shiga prefectural research institute with as many as 30 research scientists with different specialties belonging to three research groups: Cultural History and Geoscience, Biotic and Human Interactions, and Museum Studies. Owing to the diversity of researchers' specialties, research at LBM is wide ranging and interdisciplinary, dealing with a variety of aspects related to the lake and its catchment area. Many limnological projects on the lake are carried out utilizing our research boat *Umindo* (Fig. 1).

In 2020, the LBM completed a comprehensive six-year long renovation, and the results of our research and other museum activities are incorporated into the renewed displays in the four major exhibition rooms. In the Geological History exhibition room, covering the origins of the lake, the local geology and past environments, the most outstanding exhibit is a replica of a 4 m tall elephant, closely related to an extinct species that used to live in the area - viewed from one side, the skeleton is visible, from the other, the body is reconstructed. The Human History exhibition room showcases research on people's lifestyles in the past, traditional fishing methods and irrigation techniques, and historic flooding events (the highest was in 1896, with a water level of +3.76 m). A large traditional wooden cargo boat, with a design unique to Shiga Prefecture, relates how the lake used to be a major transport route. The Nature Connecting with our Lifestyles exhibition room takes an in-depth look into the lake today, its surrounding landscapes, and how humans have changed the lake and habitats. For example, one display shows how water use in the Lake Biwa catchment area has changed in the last 120 years (Fig. 2). An

Fig. 1 *Umindo*, the research boat of the LBM

is classified as one of the world's few 'ancient' lakes, with the current north basin forming about 400 000 years ago. More than 1700 species of animals, plants, and protists have been reported from the lake, some 60 of which are endemic species/subspecies. More than 450 rivers and streams flow into Lake Biwa, but there is only one natural outlet, the Seta River (Setagawa). The outflow from Lake Biwa is controlled by the Setagawa weir located on the river, and is carefully managed as even small changes in water levels of the lake are critical in shaping the littoral habitats and spawning sites of native fish (Mizuno et al. 2010, Fujioka et al. 2013).

The Lake Biwa Museum (LBM) was established in 1996, with a theme of "Lakes and People". It aims to comprehensively cover the natural history and culture of Shiga Prefecture, the area of which is almost identical to the catchment area

old rural house, which was donated to the museum, shows how life in Japan has dramatically changed since the 1960s, and how this has affected the lake. The last exhibition room or the LBM's Aquarium (Fig. 3), is one of the largest freshwater aquariums in Japan. It features many aquatic species living in and around the lake, such as the giant Biwa catfish, and many Japanese endangered fishes, carefully conserved in captivity in the LBM. Other ancient lakes in the world, such as Lake Baikal and Lake Tanganyika, are also featured. The Micro-Aquarium section displays some of the micro-fauna and flora living in the lake with the aid of microscopes, highlighting the role that these tiny species play in the ecosystem of the lake. In addition, there are two Discovery Rooms, one for children and another for adults, with hands-on exhibits and specimens that can be handled and studied. In the LBM's grounds, visitors can stroll passed reconstructions of ancient

Fig. 2 Exhibition showing changes in water use

forests, observe the tree canopies from the Treetop Walk, and enjoy an expansive view of Lake Biwa. Every year, a thematic special exhibition introduces visitors to topics about natural science or culture, organised around the research specialty of one of the LBM's research scientists.

The LBM also strongly supports citizen science activities. These activities are open from children to seniors, across all generations. There are two systems that people can join, the most well-known one, *Hashikake*, consists of 26 different groups, while there are also the *Field Reporters*. These two systems are operated mainly by citizen members with advisory assistance of the research scientists in the museum. Some research results coming from these systems have become published research papers and reports.

The LBM has cooperation agreements with some other museums and institutions that have a joint interest in aquatic environments, such as the Nakdonggang National Institute of Biological Resources in Korea, and Baikal Museum of the Siberian Branch of Russian Academy of Science. Through the agreements, joint activities, such as seminars and exhibitions, have been held, and specimens are exchanged for research and exhibits.

If you have a chance to come to Japan, we warmly welcome you to the LBM! Find out more at www.biwahaku.jp/english. You can also read about Lake Biwa in the recent book (2014) *Lake Biwa Guidebook*. Shiga Prefecture, Otsu.

Fig. 3 The tunnel tank of the Aquarium, representing the off-shore habitat of Lake Biwa

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